

Zero raised to the power zero can only take the values 1 and 0

Enrico P. G. Cadeddu *

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Abstract

Contradictions are obtained, considering all properties of powers applied to 0^0 . Limiting the rules, $0^0 = 1$ and at most $0^0 = 0$ are possible.

Introduction

The most important argument to obtain 0^0 value is considered the function definition from an empty set to an empty set. Given $f : A \rightarrow B$, with $|A|$ and $|B|$ the elements number in each set, the number of possible functions is $|B|^{|A|}$. For empty sets there is only one function, then $0^0 = 1$. But we might doubt about the existence of a function defined by two empty sets (with no element).

Other arguments, for $0^0 = 1$ or an indeterminate value, involve the coherence of certain mathematical expressions, conventions or the search for some simplicity [1] [2] [3] [4].

Here we discuss the application of the properties of powers.

0^0 is a power by definition, and we have to be able to apply rules and properties of powers, at least some of them, otherwise "0" wouldn't have the meaning of an exponent; as the rules can be deduced from its meaning.

Considering all powers properties, then also with negative exponents, we have:

$$0^0 = 0^{2-2} = 0^2 \cdot 0^{-2} = 0 \cdot 0^{-2} = 0^1 \cdot 0^{-2} = 0^{-1} = \frac{1}{0} \quad (1)$$

But $\frac{1}{0}$ is a not-existent number, having no solutions because any number multiplied by the denominator 0 gives 0 and not the numerator = 1. Then 0^0 doesn't exist, or equivalently its other possible solutions are contradictory with (1).

* Email Address cadeddu.e@gmail.com

So, to avoid 0^0 not-existence, then (1), we have to refuse some rules implying negative exponents with the number 0, therefore: $0^{a-a} \neq 0^a \cdot 0^{-a}$ (with $a \in \mathbb{R} - \{0\}$). Is $0^{-a} \neq \frac{1}{0}$ necessary for coherence?

Anyway we have to note that: $t^{a-a} = t^a \cdot t^{-a}$ and $t^{-a} = \frac{1}{t^a}$ cannot be demonstrated, with fractions and negative exponents, if $t = 0$ (in fact $\frac{0}{0}$, or similar, is an indeterminate form, not-necessary equal to 1 or other value).

Having established this, we consider:

$$x = 0^0 = 0^{0 \cdot 2} = (0^0)^2 = 0^0 \cdot 0^0 \quad (2)$$

$x = x \cdot x$ only has the two possible solutions: 0 and 1.

At the same time also we have:

$$x = 0^0 = 0^{0 \cdot (-1)} = (0^0)^{-1} = \frac{1}{0^0} \quad (3)$$

Note that (2) and (3) are valid for b^0 with $b \in \mathbb{R} - \{0\}$, $b \in \mathbb{R}$ for (2).

$x = x^{-1} = \frac{1}{x}$ only has the two possible solutions: 1 and -1. $x \neq 0$; 0 is different from $\frac{1}{0}$ (which doesn't exist) and then $x = 0$ would be contradictory. If we took $0^{-a} \neq \frac{1}{0}$, then $x = 0$ would also be possible.

The result: $0^0 \neq 0$ and $0^0 = -1$ contradicts the previous one: $0^0 = 0$ and $0^0 \neq -1$. If 0 and -1 were assigned to 0^0 we would have an absurd.

The only value in common (among (2) and (3)) is 1, then $0^0 = 1$ **isn't contradictory and it is the only possible result**, with 0 at most (taking $0^{-a} \neq \frac{1}{0}$).

In \mathbb{R}_0^+ , also $0^0 = 0$ wouldn't appear contradictory, not being able to take negative numbers (then $0^{0 \cdot (-1)}$) and consequently $0^0 \rightarrow x = \frac{1}{x}$ which would exclude 0.

References

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